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DIC Analysis of Shrinkage Behaviors of Dental Composites During Dental Restoration

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Background

❖ Polymerization shrinkage during dental restoration

- Polymerization shrinkage
- Debonding
- Contraction stress
- Crack, defect...2nd caries
- Reduction of oral-age

❖ Digital image correlation (DIC)

Previous studies

❖ Analysis of resin shrinkage using digital image correlation (DIC)

• **Analysis of local shrinkage patterns of self-adhering and flowable composites using 3D digital image correlation** *Quintessence Int.*, Vol.42(9), 2011, Miletic V, Manojlovic D, Milosevic M, Mitrovic N, Stankovic TS, Maneski T.

• **Application of digital image correlation method to study dental composite shrinkage** *Strain*, vol. 44(3), 2008, Chuang SF , Chen TY, Chang CH.

• **Polymerization shrinkage behavior of light cure resin composites in cavities** *Journal of biomechanical science and engineering*, vol. 4, 2009, Furukawa T, Arakawa K, Morita Y, Uchino M.

Purpose

This study focuses on the changes of **polymerization shrinkage distribution** examined by the **DIC method** during dental restoration for two types of composite resins, Clearfil AP-X(Kuraray, Japan) and Filtek P90 (3M ESPE, USA).

Experimental

❖ Resins

Natural-looking esthetics were achieved with an easy single-shade technique.

Composite	Polymerization shrinkage (vol %)
Clearfil AP-X (Kuraray)	1.9 ¹⁾
Filtek P90 (3M ESPE)	0.88 ²⁾

❖ Specimen ring

Material : Poly methyl Methacrylate (PMMA)

1) AP-X, scientific documentation 2003, Kuraray Co.

2) Alternative methods for determining shrinkage in restorative resin composites, Dental Materials (2011)

Digital image correlation

❖ Camera measurement for DIC

DIC measurement conditions

	During irradiation	After irradiation
Frame rate	3 f/s	10 f/s
Exposed time	0.2 ms	300 ms
Recorded time	20 s	580 s

❖ Analysis

Analysis →

Optimal conditions for measurement

DIC measurement system	ARMIS ver. 6.3.1
Section interval	0.5 mm
Facet size	17 × 17 pixels
Facet step	8 × 8 pixels
Overlap	53%

Results & Discussion

❖ Principal strain distribution of cured resins

AP-X

P90

Results & Discussion

❖ Average radial shrinkage strain of AP-X as a function of time

Results & Discussion

❖ Average radial shrinkage strain of P90 as a function of time

Results & Discussion

❖ Average radial shrinkage strain versus location radius from the center

Conclusion

In this study, polymerization shrinkage distributions of two types of composite resins, Clearfil AP-X (Kuraray, Japan) and Filtek P90 (3M ESPE, USA), were measured during dental restoration by a digital image correlation method.

- (1) The measured results by DIC method showed that the radial shrinkage strains rapidly increased for the irradiation period, but showed a different shrinkage speed at the respective radii, and converged to a constant value after irradiation stop.
- (2) The radial shrinkage strain of the resin part was the maximum near the center of the specimen, and happened to be -0.56% for Clearfil AP-X and -0.44% for Filtek P90.
- (3) The radial shrinkage strain decreased with increasing distance from the center of resin part. The radial shrinkage strain during light irradiation formed by 57% for Clearfil AP-X and by 33% for Filtek P90 of the entire radial shrinkage strain of the final cured state.